

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ARANGO LONDONO****FIRST NAME: MARIA****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: ACA-401

1. **During the writing process of a research paper, according to the *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* what is the recommended sequence to follow when starting the writing process for your paper?**
 - Select a topic, accumulate evidence, pose a question, support the proposed answer, and determine the intended audience.
 - Select a topic, pose a question, accumulate evidence from both sides, support the proposed answer and determine the intended audience.
 - Select a topic, pose a question, determine the intended audience, accumulate evidence from both sides and support the proposed answer.¹**
 - Pose a question, determine the intended audience, accumulate only supportive evidence and support the proposed answer.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1-14.

2. **Plagiarism is a serious academic offence. It can be avoided by doing the following.**

- Being consistent with the style of writing, while using the proper citing format.²**
- Being vigilant to what style of writing your paper is in and always cite regardless if you knew it before
- As long as you give credit to the author in some way, there will not be a problem
- You only need to cite if you are using direct quotes, otherwise do not worry about it. If the statement or quote is common knowledge there is no need to cite.

3. **Direct quotes are often seen throughout papers. They can vary in length and can sometimes even have their own paragraph. How and when should direct quotes be used?**

- Should be used in every paragraph followed by a summary of it in your own words.
- Direct quotes should be used rarely, in fact in areas of science they are normally not used.³**
- Try and use longer quotes in between big paragraphs to give the reader a break in information.
- It is okay to use direct quotes freely as long as they are properly cited.

4. **Harvard rule of style is said to be one of the most frequently used citing systems. Like other referencing systems the writer has to do a citation when other's ideas, theories, facts, statistics, charting etc., are used.**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *Coursepack: Period 1*, 5-12.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2015), 5.

Which of the following examples is the proper way to use the in-text citations:

- The author is cited along the publication date and page number: Smith (1995, p.534) or (Locke 1974, p.64-67).⁴**
 - Only last name and page number is needed: Smith (p.534) or (Locke p.64-67)
 - The author is cited along page number and the publication date: Smith (p.534, 1995.) or (Locke p.64-67, 1974.)
 - Unlike other styles, the Harvard rule of style does not require a page number: Smith (1995) or (Locke 1974)
5. **The process is writing an expository essay, persuasive essay etc., are all comprised of the same five steps. According to Sebranek, Kemper and Meyer, what are the steps to follow.**
- Introduce a voice, find the purpose, write and review
 - Research, outline, first draft, write, edit and publish
 - Pre-writing, writing, revising, editing and publishing.⁵**
 - Research, pre-writing, drafting, writing, editing and publishing
6. **The tentative answer you are trying to prove is the hypothesis. The core of the argument as three elements. What are those elements?**
- Your questions, your statement, and the evidence to support your statement

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *Coursepack: Period 4*, 74-80.

⁵ Patrick Sebranek et al., *Write Source 2000, A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, a division of Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 5-15.

- The answer you developed, the evidence that supports it, and the evidence that also contradicts it. (You have to show both sides of the argument)
 - Your claim, your reasons for accepting it, and the evidence that supports those reasons.⁶**
 - Your argument, why others should accept it, and the evidence that supports the argument
7. **Through what part of the writing process should the writer spend the most time double-checking facts for accuracy?**
- Research/pre-writing section
 - Publishing section
 - Editing section
 - Revision section.⁷**
8. **The use of numbers is frequently used during writing. Which form of using number is correct?**
- You are able to use both numbers and writing in a phrase as long as those between one and ten are in writing and 11 up for figures.
 - Try to stick to one during a phrase, except when two numbers are adjacent to one another then you can use both.⁸**
 - You are able to start a sentence with a figure only if the number is 100 or higher. If not, as a rule of thumb it needs to be written out.

⁶ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writing of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 37.

⁷ Sebranek et al., *Write Source 2000*, 157-228

⁸ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (n. p.: European Commission., 2011), 28-30.

- Fractions you can only combine figures and words such as (two-thirds) when they are written as nouns.
9. **The EU operates through a series of Treaties and other agreements of similar status, which together constitute _____.** Adopted under the Treaties are various legal acts that are known as the - _____.
- Primary legislation and secondary legislation.**⁹
- Regulations and directives
- National legislation and special procedural legislation
- The European Parliament and consulate
10. **To understand and develop their researching skills, the development is broken up into three steps. In order to convince your reader, you need to answer the following questions.**
- I am working on the topic X / Because I want to find out Y/ So that I can help others understand Z.**¹⁰
- I am interested in topic X/ Because I found out Y/ So I can help others understand Z
- I want to find out X/ Because I want to help others understand Y/ So my research can impact Z
- I am researching topic X/ Because I want to prove Y/ So that I can help others understand Z

⁹ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. *English Style Guide*, 58-63.

¹⁰ Turabian, 15.

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